

A SYSTEM FOR THE DESIGN AND AUTOMATED LAY-UP FOR THE MANUFACTURE OF COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY : This paper describes the development of a low cost system for the automated manufacture of composite laminates made from prepreg and dry fabric. Tackling the task of laying up composites via robotic means requires more than just mechanical ingenuity. A systems approach needs to be employed which focuses on the area adding most to a parts quality namely the design engineer. Development of the overall systems architecture has evolved by having the design engineer as the focal point. The result of this is that, not only the software and systems, but also the hardware is developed about this focus point. Automation used for the layup process enables the plies to be layed and consolidated according to the requirements of the design engineer. Information generated during the engineering draping analysis is used to control the automation. An important feature of the automated process is the relatively simple low-cost hardware used to achieve the required draping and consolidation of the plies. The system is designed for cost effective manufacturing by minimising human intervention during manufacture and the maximum exploitation of a unified computer database.

KEYWORDS: Automated Layup, Robotics, CAD/CAM/CAPPS, design for manufacture (DFM)

INTRODUCTION

Several attempts have been made to automate the layup process with varying success. In all, the result has been to provide a means for mechanically laying up the material, with little regard for the upstream processes, such as design and analysis. There has been very little synthesis between CAD/CAM and CAPPS in developing automated layup systems [2-5] although Jarvis et al [1] have made some significant inroads into synthesising the tasks. Because of the highly directional nature of fibrous composites, the misalignment of fibres whilst draping the material can produce parts with properties much different to those used by the engineer during analysis. This means that the design/analysis of the composites must be an integral part of any automated layup system for it to be used successfully in industry. Identifying that the engineer provides a pivotal role in determining a parts quality, means that the human must be considered at all stages of development from system design right through to the design of the automation.

SYSTEM PHILOSOPHY

Having the human as the focus means that the less tangible aspects of human performance need to be considered when developing the hardware for the system. These include ensuring the system provides an environment in which the design engineer is encouraged and supported in attempting to provide optimally designed parts. Such a system needs to allow the parameters used in defining the layup in the design stage to be used during manufacture so as to ensure the parts made are representative of the parts designed and analysed.

Defining the layup for a composite requires the path used to lay the ply to be fully defined. The reason being that the in plane shearing of the fabric that occurs whilst rolling out a layup path is what determines the final orientations of the fibres. Invariably the path is not considered during the design stage and hence during the layup there exists little control over replicating the orientations used in design whilst laying up. Having the path defined as part of the design allows the layup to be performed so as to replicate the path chosen. The end result is control of the fibre orientations at the design stage. Existing projects focus not on the engineer, but more on the mechanical means for holding and manipulating the fabric. As a result, the orientations for the fibres need to be assessed while performing the layup, wasting time and money, and resulting in a system unable to respond quickly to the demands of the market - thus detracting from the quality of the part.

The automation used had to reflect the demands of the system objectives, this resulted in the need to predict, upfront, the constraints imposed upon the fabric from the handling device. This could have been done using the most common handling technique of using multiple grippers and analysing their effects on constraining the ply deformation during layup. A system by Buckingham et al [2] used a similar system in which the fabric deformation was used to control the position of the ply grippers during layup. The system however, imposed a restriction on the design engineer in that the use of many grippers results in a modified draping path in order to avoid collisions between the draping robot and the grippers holding the ply. In addition the extra automation required to hold more complex plies results in increasing complexity and expense.

The system decided upon looked at clearing the entire ply area of obstructions to enable a draping path to be specified by the design-engineer, and then followed uninterrupted by the automation during layup. In addition, the system had to obviate the need to reconfigure for different shaped parts, allowing the creativity of the engineer to be exploited as optimal solutions to the part layup were investigated.

The structure of the system aims to provide a means for producing identical parts from the one set of process plans. In this way the part produced can be used as direct feedback for the engineer on its performance.

Figure 12: System Structure

COLLISION AVOIDANCE

Collision avoidance was a key issue in developing a system that focussed on the engineers decisions. If each ply needed to undergo a collision analysis to prevent the handling and draping robots from hitting one another, the draping path from design to final product is altered and the information flow becomes cluttered. This leads to reduced speeds at which the products can reach their market. Additionally, the specific design information defining the composite would be lost. The loss of information arises as robot programmers define the path needed to drape the ply to avoid collisions, hence, effectively designing the products properties by altering the fibre directions. Robot programming necessarily contains some form of manual interaction, in most cases a large portion. Again, this would reduce the ease and speed at which a product could be transformed from design to finished part.

Of the automated layup systems published, very few tackle 3D broadgoods layup, as such flat box style end effectors have sufficed for handling, avoiding the need for complex robotic manipulation. Buckingham et al [2], and Ruth et al [4], both developed systems that layed up onto 3D surfaces. Buckingham laying up onto complex curved surfaces and Ruth only onto developable singly curved surfaces. Both provide solutions for laying up using automation, however, neither provide a simple method for handling varying shaped ply without the loss of draping information. As such, they do not provide a method for effectively laying up in an environment that encourages quick time to market.

The crucial issue was to ensure the final layup was as defined by the engineer. Achieving this requires careful design of the automation and in particular, the overall system.

END EFFECTORS

Several robotic handling devices to date have been tested, none producing satisfactory results. This is due to the restrictions placed on the automation in trying to create the desired working environment. The handling devices tested have all been of a flat pad variety, as this satisfies the criteria for uninterrupted draping of the picked up ply, and also allows any shaped ply to be held. Restricting the shapes the engineers can use, restricts the creativity used during design and was considered inappropriate. Past work by Jarvis[1] and Kolluru[6] successfully used flat boxes for picking up the material. The major difference with these two projects and this one, is the objective in this project to lay up onto complex curved surfaces. For this, the pad needed to be very flexible.

The initial trials produced a suction pad that could hold and release the material without difficulty, performing the same basic tasks that both Jarvis and Kolluru's performed. Problems were encountered, however, when selectively picking of the ply from within its nested position. To overcome these, tests were preformed to determine the height at which the suction could be applied and still lift the ply. 4 mm was found to be a rough practical limit. Any ply within the 4 mm distance could be picked up, while the ply at 5 mm distance did not have the pressure differential created across it to be lifted by the suction pad. To selectively pick the ply, the pad needed to be pressed down at one point on the ply causing the ply to be sucked onto the pad. The pad and ply were then raised approximately 5 mm off the table. At this time the suction throughout the rest of the pad was activated which resulted in the parts of the ply nearest the attachment point to be sucked up onto the pad, until the entire ply was sucked up onto the pad. This method was fraught with problems, in hindsight, being a little ambitious. The pad required far too much power to apply the necessary suction, mainly due to the pressure gains along long lengths of small diameter tubing. And, due to the large air flow rate needed, the tubing supplying the suction across the pad was large and resulted in a stiff pad, unable to follow complex curved surfaces. However, for the manipulation of plies without the need to selectively pick them from a nested position, as in Kolluru's case, this end effector pad works well. For the problem at hand, however, it was not sufficient.

Work is continuing on developing an end effector suitable for the specified work environment.

CELL AUTOMATION

The automation cell used to trial the system philosophy consisted of two robots, one materials handler and the other for draping. A Mitsubishi Movemaster was used for performing the

simple pick and place movements; and a Yamaha MXY for draping. An additional degree of freedom in the vertical plane was attached to the Yamaha, allowing X, Y, Z and horizontal rotational positioning. In addition to this the rotational degree of freedom of the Yamaha was supplemented with an end effector able to rotate in the vertical plane. This was used for orientating the end effector so that it was normal to the tool surface. The resulting configuration allowed for positioning of the end effector normal to the surface anywhere over the three dimensional contoured tool. Although the setup provided many limitations (one of the major ones being that three separate controllers were being used to control the positioning) its purpose was to set a base structure for a manufacturing cell capable of working with the system philosophy.

The Movemaster was used to hold a frame with the pad attached. Using only one robot for robot handling limited the size of the ply to test pieces of around 250 mm square. The Yamaha had an airline attached, capable of applying 20 N of force onto the ply, a force found by [1] and individual tests, to be representative of light manual rolling. Using air pressure to generate the force meant that larger forces were possible for those regions that were difficult to lay (ie. required more shearing force to fit the contour). Positioning of the Yamaha was controlled from data extracted from the computer draping model.

The basic procedure involved sending the pick and place robot the coordinates (extracted from a shape nesting file) for picking up the ply. The ply was picked up and moved to the correct position in the tool, at which point the draping robot forces the ply down using pressurised air. The path traversed by the robot is defined by the design engineer in the computer draping model. This path, along with the tool surface geometry, define the resulting fibre orientations and ply shape.

When finished the proposed operations are for the draping robot to move away, clearing the area, and the pick and place robot to return for the next ply. The afore mentioned problems with the end effector for handling the ply has prevented a full run of the system to be performed to date.

SOFTWARE

The software is used to provide a means for effortlessly convert the computer model of the part into process plans for laying up. It does this by searching the computer model for the data needed to develop the process plan. The process plan for controlling the automation is automatically generated for each of the plies in the model. Once generated, the process plan can be executed at the computer terminal. To use the software, an interface is used, Figure 2, in which the user simply chooses the computer model file, and the file containing the nested ply data. Next the button labelled '1- Run Analysis' is pressed to analysis the data and generate the process plans. This step generates:

- the information for scanning the flat ply
- coordinate data to control the draping robot over the contoured surface (Figure 3)
- coordinate data for controlling the robot to locate and place the ply
- data for operating the high pressure air lines during layup
- the entire process plan for laying up the part (a program created by combining the results from 1-4)

Figure 13: Software Interface

Following the generation of the plans the user will then be able to press the button ‘2- Begin Layup’ and activate the automation to begin the layup.

In the test case, no automated cutter was available so positioning of cut plies has been done by hand to represent the location of a nested ply cut using an automated cutter. A file containing the relative positions of the automation is created by the user when the automation is first set up. The positioning of plies was achieved using a common axis system throughout the entire computer design process, and referencing this in the beginning to the cutting table origin. The software uses this common axis system to generate the final process plan.

Figure 14: Computer generated draping sequence

CONCLUSIONS

A system philosophy has been created with the objective of improving the quality of laminated composites in regards to the demands of today's global work environment. In doing this the focus has been on developing a system able to provide the design engineers with the means for realising their designs during manufacture. The software has been developed that simplifies the process such that the engineer remains the focus, and although the hardware to compliment the system has been tested as a trial manufacturing cell with mixed success, the basic principles for a workable system have been tested.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. D. H. Jarvis, Wilcox, K., Chen X.Q., McCarthy R., Sarhadi M., "Design of a Handling Device for Composite Ply Lay-up Automation," *IEEE*, 1991.
- [2] R. O. Buckingham and G. C. Newell, "Automating the Manufacture of Composite Broadgoods," *Composites Part A*, vol. 27A, pp. 191-200, 1996.
- [3] G. C. Newell, R. O. Buckingham, and K. Khodabundehloo, "The Automated Manufacture of Prepreg Broadgoods Components - a Review of the Literature," *Composites Part A*, vol. 27A, pp. 211-217, 1996.
- [4] D. E. Ruth and P. Mulgaonkar, "Robotic Lay-up of Prepreg Composite Plies," presented at IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, 1990.
- [5] R. B. Hans-Joachim Becker, "Industrial Multi-arm Handling System for Automated Manufacture of Composite Broadgoods," *17th June 1992 IEEE Colloquium Multi-arm Robotics*, 1992.
- [6] R. Kolluru, K. P. Valavanis, A. Steward, and M. Sonnier, "A Flat-Surface Robotic Gripper for Handling Limp Material," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine*, 1995.